

THE PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO
THE STUDY OF THE TRIAD -N·C·S-. PART V. ACTION
OF NITROUS ACID ON $\alpha\alpha'$ -METHYL-
PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDE.

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Mehta and Krall (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1935, 12, 635, 640) studied the action of nitrous acid on monophenylthiocarbamide and found that two changes occurred simultaneously : (i) oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide to Hector's base, and (ii) the "normal" reaction of nitrous acid on amides with the production phenylmustard oil and further they found that strong acids facilitated the former change, weak acids the latter.

The same reaction has now been extended to $\alpha\alpha'$ -methylphenylthiocarbamide with the object of ascertaining the effect of the presence of a positive group.

In the presence of hydrochloric acid, an evanescent wine-red colouration is produced suggesting the transient formation of a thionitrite (Tasker and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1917), whilst a gas consisting chiefly of NO (83 %) is rapidly evolved, the reaction mixture containing a base which yields a crystalline perchlorate and picrate and appears to be methylphenylformamidine disulphide formed thus :

The simultaneous occurrence of a subsidiary reaction, just as in the parent compound, is shown by the evolution of nitrogen (17%) and the presence in the reaction mixture of sulphuric acid (10%), methylaniline and some solid. The base is prone to further oxidation and when larger proportions of sodium nitrite are used, an oil is produced, whilst the amount of the solid, sulphuric acid, NO and nitrogen is correspondingly increased. Traces of COS and CO₂ are also present in the gas phase.

In the presence of acetic acid, on the other hand, sodium nitrite reacts slowly with the thiocarbamide and the gas phase is mostly nitrogen (85%) but it contains also carbon oxysulphide. No formamidine disulphide is produced and the evolution of nitrogen, agreeing with the action of

phenylthiocarbamide in the same conditions, suggests the normal behaviour of amides, and the product formed might be expected to decompose into

methylaniline and carbon oxysulphide. Free methylaniline is not found but the reaction mixture contains two solids and an oil of complex character, evidently resulting from the mutual interaction of the above substances. In this case the oxidation reaction is a subsidiary one, nitric oxide being produced in smaller quantity (5%). Excess of sodium nitrite brings about secondary decompositions as in the presence of hydrochloric acid.

It is clear, therefore, that nitrous acid acts on α -methylphenylthiocarbamide according to the following equations :

The presence of acids facilitates the former change. The evolution of nitrogen in (ii) is an evidence for the structure (I) which is thus the predominant tautomer in neutral solutions. Acids evidently facilitate the change of this to a form which does not contain the amino group as in (II).

(I)

(II)

It will be noticed that while phenylthiocarbamide yields a diazothiol (Hector's base) with the greatest ease by oxidation with various reagents, including nitrous acid, methylphenylthiocarbamide, which gives such a diazothiol with iodine or hydrogen peroxide (Gabriel and Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1578; Chakrabarti and De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 661) gives a formamidine disulphide with nitrous acid, thereby resembling thiocarbamide itself (Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2180). There is no evidence that the formamidine disulphides break down to diazothiois and in the light of the present investigation it appears that Hector's base, which is produced with extreme ease under these conditions from the parent compound, is a direct oxidation product of phenylthiocarbamide and that no intermediate

disulphide compound need be postulated (*cf.* Fromm and Heyder, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 3804). The proximity of the methyl group to the phenyl nucleus in the methyl homologue seems, however, to prevent oxidation into a Hector's base the production of which is, therefore, dependent on the free α -hydrogen atom. The feeble base obtained by Dost (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 1014) by the action of sulphuryl chloride on the methylphenylthiocarbamide in chloroform solutions does not appear to be formed under our conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All the gasometric experiments were carried out in a Lunge's nitrometer. It was found convenient to use a solution of sodium nitrite containing one mg. molecule NaNO_2 per c.c. The requisite amount of sodium nitrite was added by introducing definite volume of this solution with the aid of 1 c.c. pipette graduated in tenths of a cubic centimetre.

Expt. i. Action of Nitrous Acid on α -Methylphenylthiocarbamide in presence of N-Hydrochloric Acid (Gas phase).—0.083 G. of thiocarbamide ($\frac{1}{3}$ mg.) was introduced into the nitrometer with the help of 1 c.c. of alcohol. To enable the reaction to begin in acid solution, 1 c.c. of 4N-hydrochloric acid* was added before the addition of the nitrite solution. The cup of the nitrometer was then washed down with 0.5 c.c. of water. The above solution was then treated with 0.5 c.c. of sodium nitrite solution ($\frac{1}{3}$ mg.) and the cup of the nitrometer further washed with 1 c.c. of water. The reaction was brisk and invariably took place with the production of an evanescent wine-red colour. The reaction mixture becomes finally pale yellow and the evolution of the gas was complete in half an hour. Gas collected, 127 c.c. at 22° and 748 mm., *i.e.*, 11.3 c.c. at N. T. P. and contained N, 17; NO, 83 per cent.

The gas evolved in the above experiment was expelled from the nitrometer and 0.5 c.c. of NaNO_2 solution ($\frac{1}{3}$ mg.) more added to the residual liquid in the nitrometer. 9.8 C.c. of the gas at N. T. P. were further evolved with the production of a slight red colouration and contained N, 38% ; NO, 50% ; COS + CO₂, 12% (determined by absorption in concentrated alkali, *cf.* *Expt. 4*). It was observed that upto five molecular proportions of nitrous acid could thus react to produce mainly secondary decomposition in which the proportion of the residual gas left after treatment with alkali and FeSO_4 solutions rose up to 40% of the total gas evolved. This residual gas was wholly nitrogen because it was unaffected by

* To avoid unnecessary dilution, acid of this strength was used.

ammoniacal cuprous chloride solution and by bromine, showing the absence of CO or unsaturated hydrocarbons

In these experiments sulphuric acid was detected in the residual liquid left behind in the nitrometer. There was no evidence of the production of thiocyanic acid or free sulphur during the reaction. This experiment was next done on a large scale to study more closely other reaction products, neglecting those present in the gas phase.

Expt. 2. Action of Nitrous Acid on $\alpha\alpha'$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide in Molecular proportions in presence of N-Hydrochloric Acid, neglecting the Gas Phase.—Hydrochloric acid (4 N-, 100 c.c.) was added to the cold solution of $\alpha\alpha'$ -methylphenylthiocarbamide (8.3 g.) in 200 c.c. of 50 % warm alcohol in a 500 c.c. flask. The flask was kept in a water-bath at a temperature of 19-20°. A solution of 3.5 g. of sodium nitrite (98.5 % pure) in 100 c.c. of water was slowly added to the thiocarbamide solution, with constant shaking during the course of an hour. The red colouration produced on the addition of the nitrite solution persisted more or less for about 25 minutes. The solution then turned pale yellow and more addition of the nitrite solution did not produce further change in colouration. After the addition of the nitrite solution the flask was put aside for an hour to complete the reaction. Small amount of solid separated which when viewed under the microscope appeared to be those produced in larger amount in presence of acetic acid (*cf. Expt. 5*). There was no separation of sulphur during the experiment. The solution was filtered from the insoluble matter and the clear filtrate examined as follows:

(a) 50 C.c. of the solution were just neutralised with ammonia when an emulsion was formed which on stirring gave rise to a reddish-brown oil. The supernatant liquid was carefully decanted, the oil washed with a little water and extracted with ether. About 0.5 c.c. of the oil, obtained from the ethereal extract, was treated with 1 c.c. of 4N-hydrochloric acid when an immediate separation of sulphur took place. The acid solution was decanted off the residual oily matter. It gave Libermann's nitrosoamine reaction, suggesting the presence of methylaniline formed in the original reaction mixture. The oil decomposed by itself into sulphur and other product when it was heated at 80° or kept as such overnight. There was, however, no precipitation of any base, corresponding to Hector's base in the parent compound, on neutralisation of the acid reaction mixture.

(b) 200 C.c. of the original acid mixture were boiled under reflux for an hour. It shortly turned slightly pink and got turbid. The pink colour

disappeared but the turbidity was latter followed by the production of a light yellow mass of sulphur (0.21 g.). The residual mother liquor from this contained thiocyanic acid, undoubtedly formed as a result of the hydrolysis of some free thiocarbamide which was in fact detected in the residues obtained by evaporating the reaction mixture to dryness. The same sequence of changes occurs in the original reaction mixture if it is kept as such for several days.

(c) 50 C.c. of saturated ammonium perchlorate solution were added to 50 c.c. of the acid reaction mixture when an emulsion was produced which separated as an oil the next day. When placed in a vacuum over sulphuric acid it solidified to a brittle mass. It was crystallised from methyl alcohol and ether by cooling in ice, m.p. 143° (decomp.). It contains N, S, Cl and on boiling in aqueous solution it decomposes to give products as in (b) above.

(d) 50 C.c. of 1% aqueous picric acid solution were added to 50 c.c. of the reaction mixture. An amorphous yellow mass at once separated. This was found to be due to the presence of methylaniline in the original solution. The liquid was decanted off this amorphous mass. A light yellow precipitate was formed on keeping overnight which was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 140° . It contains S and N and decomposes on boiling with water like the perchlorate. When the precipitate of the picrate was crystallised from hot ethyl alcohol, some of it seemed to decompose into sulphur and other products.

(e) 50 C.c. of the acid solution were treated with a solution of barium chloride. The BaSO_4 so obtained weighed 0.1382 g. pointing to the oxidation of about 10% sulphur to sulphuric acid. The behaviour of the acid reaction mixture thus suggested the presence of methylphenylformamidine disulphide hydrochloride in solution to which decompositions, mentioned in (a) and (b), could be attributed. Moreover, the formation of a crystalline perchlorate and a picrate from the aqueous solution confirmed the presence of this base in solution. The salts of this base with most of the commoner acids appeared to be extremely soluble or else products of indefinite oily character.

If in this experiment two or more molecular proportions of sodium nitrite were employed, the reaction was marked by the production of an oil (*vide* expt. 5), more solid and sulphuric acid.

Expt. 3. Action of Nitrous Acid on $\alpha\alpha'$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide in presence of Acetic Acid (1st phase).— Methylphenylthiocarbamide

(0.083 g.) was introduced into the cup of the nitrometer with the aid of 1 c.c. of alcohol. To enable the reaction to begin under nearly neutral conditions 0.5 c.c. of sodium nitrite solution was added before the addition of 2 c.c. of 2*N*-acetic acid solution to the thiocarbamide in the nitrometer. The liquid got turbid at first and then gas was evolved in an hour. The residual liquid contained no thiocyanic acid and only traces of sulphuric acid. Gas evolved, 11.8 c.c. at 23° and 749 mm. *i.e.*, 10.4 c.c. at N.T.P and contained N, 85%; NO, 5%. COS, 10%. (*cf.* Expt. 4). In this case also, more addition of nitrite solution evolved more gas in which the proportion of nitrogen was however less (48%).

In the gasometric experiments 1 and 3 it was found that a gas' was also evolved which imparted a yellowish tinge to strong solution of alkali which then gave test for sulphide. In the following experiment this gas was subject to closer examination.

Expt. 4. Examination of the Sulphurous Gas produced in Expts. 1 and 3.—*aa'*-Methylphenylthiocarbamide (8.3 g.) was dissolved in 200 c.c. of 50% alcohol contained in a 750 c.c. round-bottomed flask. Sodium nitrite (3.5 g.) dissolved in 100 c.c. of water was further added to the cold thiocarbamide solution. 100 c.c. of 2*N*-acetic acid were then gradually added to the above solution and the temperature was kept at 22°. The evolved gas was successively driven through three absorption flasks containing the following reagents:

- (i) Saturated copper sulphate solution acidified with its own volume of concentrated sulphuric acid (50 c.c.).
- (ii) 33% Aqueous caustic potash solution (50 c.c.).
- (iii) Alcoholic caustic potash solution (30 c.c.).

No precipitate of CuS was formed in (i), whilst (ii) had a yellowish tinge which later disappeared. The alkaline solution in (ii) gave a feeble test for sulphide. The alcoholic solution in (iii), however, gave no test with sodium nitroprusside or lead acetate in the cold but on boiling the solution, lead acetate gave a copious precipitate of lead sulphide. Also the alcoholic solution did not give any precipitate with dilute copper sulphate solution, showing the absence of carbon disulphide in the gas. These observations show that the gas is COS.

In this experiment it was observed that the reaction flask contained some brown oily mass adhering to a solid. The solid was freed from the

oil by digesting with alcohol, yield 2.8 g. In another experiment it was found that the amount of the oil was greater when larger proportions of nitrous acid were used, whilst the amount of the solid was not greatly affected (3 g.). In the next experiment the solid and the oil were investigated.

Expt. 5. Examination of the Products of the Reaction formed in presence of Acetic Acid, Neglecting the Gas Phase.—The solid isolated in the above experiment was found to be a mixture of two compounds which are hard to separate by means of the common organic solvents. A chloroform-alcoholic solution of these solids, however, deposited the more insoluble constituent in blocks. The latter compound softened at 192° and melted at 199° (decomp.). [Found: N, 7.59, 7.55; S 34.44, 34.6; M.W. (Rast's method), 380]. It was not acted upon by dilute acid and alkali but was slowly attacked by concentrated acid and alkali on prolonged boiling. In the decomposition with alkali some sulphide was detected in the decomposition products but in neither case free methylaniline could be detected in the products of the reaction, though there was evidence of the presence of a secondary amino group. An alcoholic suspension of 0.3196 g. of the solid when boiled for 4 hours with ammoniacal silver nitrate gave 0.8830 g. of Ag_2S showing that all of the sulphur in the compound could thus be removed by this reagent. (Theory required Ag_2S , 0.8421 g.). Mercuric oxide was less effective for this purpose. In both these cases the alcoholic solution obtained after desulphurisation was coloured violet which gave a water-soluble residue on evaporation to dryness. Alkaline lead acetate remained unaffected when so treated with the solid. These properties and the analytical results rather point to the probable molecular formula of this compound to be $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}(\text{Me})\text{CS}_2]_2\text{O}$.

The more soluble compound (in p. 205°-10°) was obtained from the chloroform-alcoholic mother liquors in fine needles. It was still contaminated with a small amount of the above compound which could not be removed even after repeated crystallisations from toluene. It contained nitrogen (10%) and sulphur (23%). It resembled in most of its properties with the previous compound but differed from the latter in that it gave thiocyanic acid with alcoholic ammonia. The oil usually obtained in these experiments (*cf. Expts. 2 and 4*) was found to distil at 230° and was volatile in steam. It was not soluble in acids and alkalis and gave thiocyanic acid with alcoholic ammonia. The aqueous mother liquor that remained in experiment 4 did not contain free methylaniline.

The action of nitrous acid on the *sym*-methylphenylthiocarbamide is in progress.

SUMMARY.

1. Nitrous acid reacts with α -methylphenylthiocarbamide in strongly acid solution to produce mainly an oxidation change to methylphenylformamidine disulphide.
2. In the presence of weak acids the principal reaction results in the evolution of nitrogen.
3. These results are best explained by assuming that methylphenylthiocarbamide exists in neutral solution mainly as $\text{Ph}(\text{Me})\text{NCSNH}_2$, whilst the presence of acids causes the imino tautomer $\text{Ph}(\text{Me})\text{NC}(\text{SH})\text{NH}$ to predominate.
4. No diazothiol, corresponding to Hector's base in the case of the parent compound, is formed under the conditions of our experiments.

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